

A RAPID METHOD TO COMPUTE THE TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION IN NON-CRIMP FABRIC COMPOSITES

C.-S. Liao, A. Labun and A. S. Milani
School of Engineering, University of British Columbia Okanagan
3333 University Way, Kelowna, B.C. Canada V1V 1V7
csliao@interchange.ubc.ca, andrew.labun@ubc.ca, abbas.milani@ubc.ca

SUMMARY

A rapid and accurate network method, originally developed for integrated circuit interconnects, is under study for temperature distribution estimation in fabric composites. An application to biaxial non-crimp fabric composites is shown, where the solution is based on the steady-state analytical heat equation and a symbolic calculation procedure.

Keywords: non-crimp fabric, simulation, heat transfer, temperature distribution

ABSTRACT

The simulation of the temperature distribution in a biaxial non-crimp fabric is achieved with an analytical, symbolic network approach that was originally used for the heat solution of integrated circuit interconnects. The fabric composite is modelled by a network of interconnects with temperature-dependent thermal conductivity k^{long} , with vias representing contact between the overlapping fibre yarns. Analytical solutions to the heat equation along each interconnect can provide accuracy and require the minimum number of symbolic network nodes. The LU decomposition of the symbolic network scales as the cube of the number of nodes. However, subsequent evaluations, including iterative improvement of k^{long} to achieve a self-consistent solution, scale linearly with the number of nodes and hardly affect the total solution time. Finally, the new network calculation method is compared to a finite element analysis using ABAQUS.

INTRODUCTION

A number of composite components in the aerospace, automotive, marine and construction industries are built of woven textile preforms. They can give excellent mechanical properties with very low weights, but their complex fabrication processes occasionally make them expensive for composite manufacturers. As an alternative, non-crimp fabrics (NCFs) have proven to provide fairly good mechanical properties while maintaining low weight and providing cost effective solutions through their simplified fabrication processes. NCF composites are fabricated from preforms with multiple layers of straight fibre bundles that can be oriented in different directions and stitched together by a (warp) knitting procedure. Previous studies by Dransfield, Jain and Mai

showed that out-of-plane fracture toughness and damage tolerance properties of these materials are also improved through the stitching process [1].

There are numerous works that are dedicated to mechanical, thermal and other physical properties of woven and non-woven fabrics. To name a few, Bibo, Hogg and Kemp studied the elastic properties of several warp-knitted (non-crimp) fabric materials under tension and compression [2]; Drapier and Wisnom investigated the interlaminar shear behaviour of non-crimp-fabric-based composites [3]; Tessitore and Riccio performed Finite Element Method (FEM) modelling for biaxial extension of non-crimp fabric composite materials [4]. Hind, Robitaille and Raizenne conducted numerical studies on the effective thermal conductivity of a plain weave [5]. Nordlund et al. [6] and Lundström [7] have performed both numerical and experiential studies on the permeability of NCFs. Ning and Chou [8], using a closed-form representation of the transverse thermal conductivity, derived a thermal resistance network; Xu and Wirtz [9], employing a simple-to-fabricate woven mesh, described the in-plane effective thermal conductivity of two-dimensional bonded-laminate plain-weave screen laminates.

The majority of the numerical studies on the mechanical and/or thermal analysis of fabrics have been based on the meso-level FE analysis of unit cells representing repetitive (network) patterns in the fabrics. In practice, however, fabric unit cells are not perfectly repetitive (owing to uncertainties during fabric fabrication processes) and/or unsymmetrical loading conditions for a given problem can require performing analyses on larger representative volumes. As the size of the problem scales, the solution complexity and the simulation run time can pose a problem. In addition, the selection of the position of a unit cell and the associated boundary conditions can be highly important. A new method called Therminator3D, which was originally developed for integrated circuit (IC) interconnects by Labun, is capable of simulating temperature distributions of an entire thermal network rapidly and accurately, without relying on the unit cell descriptions [10]. Therminator3D applies network simulation concepts with technological parameters extracted from CAD layout descriptions to the entire network (similar to FE models). A brief review of the method in its original format for thermo-electrical analyses is presented below.

Consider the Joule self-heat generated by electric current flowing through a resistive conductor. In an IC, multiple active devices (e.g. transistors) are connected electrically by a metal interconnect network, or “net” of uniform-width resistor segments, connected at their endpoints, or “nodes” that may be “extracted” into a file. Any system of 1-D boundary value equations, such as the steady-state heat conduction, can be solved over the entire net by concatenating the individual solutions on each resistor segment. Therminator3D applies the Crout algorithm for LU decomposition and back-substitution to the system and records only the non-null operations, thus forming a generic symbolic solution for the entire net. This symbolic solution is then evaluated with electrical parameters to solve the electrical problem first, and then evaluated again with thermal parameters to solve the resulting Joule heat problem. The resistance of each resistor will itself increase with the increasing temperature. The final resistance and temperature is therefore found iteratively. Also, thermal conductance through the insulator between adjacent resistors on different nets may be extracted in the same way as capacitive coupling for IC interconnect. By composing the ambient, reference temperature for each resistor from the temperatures of resistors to which it couples

through the dielectric, it is possible to iteratively couple separate nets' temperature trajectories. To form the symbolic solution requires $O(N^3)$ operations, but for a sparse system such as an interconnect network there are only $O(N)$ non-null operations (where N is the number of nodes). Thus, the electrical and thermal *evaluations* require only $O(N)$ operations. Therminator3D requires a database that contains network information, such as the nodal relationships, coupling between resistors, input sources, and boundary conditions. A netlist file extracted from IC layout with a standard CAD tool would be the most common source of this information.

In this work, we attempted to treat thermal problems of NCFs using the concepts of Therminator3D outlined above. An auxiliary program was established to create netlist files to describe the thermal (resistor) network properties of a biaxial NCF, including the thermal conductance of each segment. It also creates additional, virtual segments around the edges of the fabric to impose appropriate boundary conditions. The goal is to use the modified interconnect net-based method to rapidly estimate the temperature distribution on the NCF. A major benefit of the method is that it relies on a symbolic, semi-analytical, and net-based approach which can reduce the computational time and enhance the accuracy of the results at full resolution. Illustrative examples, both linear and non-linear, are chosen to show the application of the method and results are compared to a finite element analysis. A simple multi-physics problem is also presented.

BASIC PHYSICAL MODEL

Figures 1(a) and (b) show two typical choices of representative volume element (RVE) of a typical biaxial non-crimp fabric. A typical interconnect network model with vias considered in Therminator3D is shown in Figure 1(c), here to represent the NCF material. The geometrical definition of thermal resistor network used is shown in Figure 1(d). The NCF perform is considered to be dry and stitches to hold the 0 and 90-degree fibre bundles together are not included in this idealized model. Each yarn segment's thermal resistance can be specified from the known properties of the fibre material. Segment length can be arbitrarily chosen for desired accuracy of the temperature distribution results.

Figure 1: (a) Typical unit cell of a biaxial NCF, e.g. for permeability/CFD analysis [6], (b) a closed-form RVE, e.g., for mechanical/thermal analysis, (c) a net-based interconnect model with vias shown with an 'X' (in this case the net includes resistors and current sources), and (d) the definition of a thermal resistor network with a via (i.e., the vertical resistor connecting the column and row to represent their contact).

Treating a segment of fibre yarn as a thermal resistor, R , we may define

$$R_{nm} = L_{nm} / k_{nm} A_{nm} \quad (1)$$

where L is the segment length, k is its thermal conductivity, and A is its cross-sectional area; the nm subscript refers to the row and column position of the segment in the network .

NETWORK CALCULATION METHOD

Considering a segment of length Δx on the thermal resistor network (Figure 2), its heat transfer problem can be written as [10]:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T(x,t)}{\partial t} = F(x + \Delta x) - F(x) + \phi(x)\Delta x - f(x)\Delta x. \quad (2)$$

The longitudinal heat flux, F , opposite to the increasing direction- x , obeys Fourier's law: $F(x) = G^{long} \partial T(x) / \partial x$. G^{long} is a thermal conductance found by integrating thermal conductivity k^{long} over the resistor cross-section. The lateral heat flux is written as $f(x) = G^{lat} (T(x) - T^{ref})$ with the thermal conductance G^{lat} representing the *diffusion* of heat flux from the sides of the resistor, through an insulating medium with thermal conductivity k^{lat} , to a uniform reference temperature T^{ref} . ρ is the material density and C_p denotes the specific heat. ϕ is the distributed heat source, e.g., Joule self-heat generated from a current in the circuit: $\phi = RI_{rms}^2$; R in this case refers to the electrical resistance.

In a steady-state case, $T(x,t)$ is a function of x only, and when $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$, Eq. (2) becomes a second order ordinary differential equation of x as follows.

$$\phi = -G^{long} d^2 T / dx^2 + G^{lat} (T - T^{ref}) \quad (3)$$

The solution on each resistor segment of length L with boundary conditions $T(x=0)=T_0$ and $T(x=L)=T_L$ is then given by [10]

$$T(x) = \left(\frac{T_L - T^\infty - (T_0 - T^\infty) \cosh(\xi L)}{\sinh(\xi L)} \right) \sinh(\xi x) + (T_0 - T^\infty) \cosh(\xi x) + T^\infty \quad (4)$$

where $\xi = \sqrt{G^{lat} / G^{long}}$ and $T^\infty = \frac{\phi}{G^{lat}} + T^{ref}$. For resistors such as vias for which $G^{lat}=0$ the solution becomes

$$T(x) = -\frac{\phi x^2}{2G^{long}} + \left(\frac{T_L - T_0}{L} + \frac{\phi L}{2G^{long}} \right) x + T_0 \quad (5)$$

For a fabric material structure, G^{long} may be attributed to the effective thermal conductance of the yarns (see, e.g., [8]) and G^{lat} to the separation between yarns. The system of boundary value equations (4), (5) can be analyzed over the fabric network by the same nodal equations used in electric circuit analyses in the study [10].

Figure 2: (a) Heat conservation within a differential slice of a one-dimensional thermal resistor accounts for longitudinal flux, lateral flux, and Joule self-heat. The heat equation solution on resistors with (b) and without (c) lateral thermal conductance can be represented by equivalent circuit networks (d) and (e). The equivalent quantities are given as [10]: $\alpha = G^{long} \xi / \sinh(\xi L)$, $\psi = 2\phi (\cosh(\xi L) - 1) / (\xi \sinh(\xi L))$, $\beta = \alpha (\cosh(\xi L) - 1)$ for interconnect elements, and $\alpha = G^{long} / L$, $\psi = \phi L$ for vias.

Nonlinear Cases: Temperature-Dependent Thermal Coefficients

In Theminator3D the thermal conductivity k^{long} is related to the electrical conductivity σ by the well-known Wiedemann-Franz law [11]

$$k^{long} = \lambda T \sigma, \quad (6)$$

where λ is a constant and T is the absolute temperature. Accordingly, the temperature-temperature-dependent σ is related to the temperature-dependent k^{long} (see also Figure 3).

Figure 3: Example of thermal and electrical conductivity variation as a function of temperature (material: copper).

Symbolic Solution

The sparse $N \times N$ system of linear algebraic equations

$$Az = b \quad (7)$$

can be decomposed into lower and upper triangular matrices L and U in order $O(N^3)$ operations by the Crout algorithm, and the system can be evaluated for z by two consecutive back-substitution operations ($O(N)$ if null operations are not performed):

$$A = LU \quad (8)$$

$$Ly = b \quad (9)$$

$$Uz = y \quad (10)$$

The elements l_{ij} and u_{ij} of L and U are found by Eqs. (11), (12) and (13) over the elements a_{ij} of A (see, e.g., [12,13]).

$$l_{ij} = 0, \text{ for } i < j, \quad u_{ij} = 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq N, \quad (11)$$

and $u_{ij} = 0$, for $i > j$, where $1 \leq i, j \leq N$

$$l_{im} = a_{im} - \sum_{\mu=1}^{m-1} l_{i\mu} u_{\mu m}, \quad i = m, m+1, \dots, N \quad (12)$$

$$u_{mj} = \frac{1}{l_{mm}} \left(a_{mj} - \sum_{\mu=1}^{m-1} l_{m\mu} u_{\mu j} \right), \quad j = m+1, m+2, \dots, N \quad (13)$$

A Fortran implementation of the symbolic solution of a sparse system was developed by Gustavson, Liniger and Willoughby [13]. Therminator3D, a C language program, applies dynamic storage allocation and data structures to store the symbolic structure of the solution. Each resistor in the net-list file is given a data structure containing all numerical data and results for the problem to be solved. All the resistor structures are referenced through 'hash' tables. The problem matrix A is represented by a linked list of $O(N)$ non-null elements of A . The vector b consists of links to heat source elements and boundary conditions. Then matrix A is decomposed into the L and U linked lists by the Crout factorization formulas. Vectors z and y are constructed as linked lists pointing to components of L , U , and b . After the entire system of linked lists has been created, it is straightforward to evaluate the specific physical problem (mechanical, thermal, electrical, etc) using an appropriate symbolic substitution. For thermal problems, the temperature trajectories $T(x)$ are determined after the z vector (the temperature of each node) has been found. Average and maximum values are stored in the data structure for convenience. The $O(N)$ evaluation can be iterated for nonlinear problems (for example when k^{long} is temperature-dependent) or for multiphysics/coupled problems.

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

A dry biaxial NCF structure made of copper is considered. Only longitudinal and overlap contact thermal conduction is assumed (i.e. $G^{lat} \rightarrow 0$ for all rows and columns of the network). This was done to simplify the problem for comparison purposes with FE models. The size and computational cost of Therminator3D analysis is not significantly affected by the neglect of lateral thermal conduction [10]. It is also assumed that there

is no Joule self-heating and no heat loss into the environment (adiabatic condition). Vias, with relatively small dimensions compared to the interconnect ($G^{lat} = 0$), represent a perfect thermal contact between overlapping yarns. Nodal temperature (i.e., essential) and thermal flux (i.e., free) types of boundary conditions were achieved using equivalent current sources and resistors at the end of corresponding rows/columns.

The first test problem solved is shown in Figure 4, which consists of a four-by-four, two-layer grid. The thermal conductivity was assumed to be temperature-independent. Values of the material properties and dimensions used are given in Table 1. The resulting temperature distribution in the network was calculated by Therminator3D and is shown in Figure 5(a). A similar model was established in the ABAQUS finite element package with automatic incrementation and the temperature contours were obtained (Figure 5(b)). Figure 6(a) shows the temperature variation along column 3, obtained by T3D and ABAQUS. Next, the procedure was repeated by allowing a variation of conductivity with temperature as shown in Figure 3. Comparison of results for the new nonlinear case is shown in Figure 6(b). Table 2 also includes results for an unbalanced NCF where the thermal conductivity value of fibre bundles 5-8 is doubled with respect to fibre bundles 1-4.

Figure 4: An NCF represented by a two-layer interconnect grid with vias showing approximate segmentation into connected resistors. All endpoint temperatures are set to $T = 0^\circ\text{C}$ except $T = 100^\circ\text{C}$ is applied to one end of interconnect/fibre bundle 3.

Table 1: Material properties of the balanced NCF used.

Row/Column Material	Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)	Interconnect Dimensions (WxHxL) (μm)	Vias Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)
Cu	4.01	10 x 10 x 100	4.01

Table 2 compares the CPU time required for these examples using T3D and ABAQUS on an Apple MacBook. The temperature trajectory for the temperature-independent thermal resistance case is found in a single T3D evaluation. As compared to ABAQUS, the convergence of the self-consistent temperature calculation for the temperature dependent case was faster in T3D due to the linear time required for the evaluation of the symbolic solution. From Figure 6, we notice that in ABAQUS we require a larger number of elements to achieve a temperature distribution almost identical to that of T3D with 80 elements (this would suggest that the convergence rate of solution during mesh refinements would be faster in T3D).

Figure 5: The column 3 temperature trajectory for the network in Figure 4, computed by T3D (left) and Abaqus (right) for a balanced NCF.

Figure 6: The row 3 temperature trajectory for the network in Figure 4, computed by T3D and ABAQUS with thermal resistance independent (a) and dependent (b) of temperature (results are for the balanced fabric case).

Table 2: Comparison of Therminator3D and ABAQUS CPU times for the heat analysis of a 4x4 metal non-crimp structure. Each value shown is the average of three repeats of a computer experiment; note that due to the variation of actual user- and system-time from one repeat to another, the total time on the same machine can be non-repeatable. Values in parentheses refer to the CPU times normalized by the number of temperature nodes (~DOF).

	T3D	ABAQUS	ABAQUS
No. of Elements	80	80	640
CPU Time (sec) for Temperature Independent, Balanced NCF Example	0.055 (6.88E-04)	1.63 (4.64E-03)	3.03 (2.01E-03)
CPU Time (sec) for Temperature Dependent, Balanced NCF Example	0.056 (7.00E-04)	1.53 (4.36E-03)	2.93 (1.94E-03)
CPU Time (sec) for Temperature Dependent, Unbalanced NCF Example	0.057 (7.13E-04)	1.66 (4.73E-03)	2.96 (1.96E-03)

Finally, a fourth example was chosen to demonstrate the application of T3D for electro-thermal analyses of fabrics (e.g., for E-textiles where electronic components are embedded into a fabric structure). The same NCF geometry of the previous examples was considered and an electric current was applied to interconnect 3 (Figure 7(a)). In this case, the Joule heat creates a body heat flux throughout interconnect 3. The result of the network calculation is shown in Figure 7(b). Self-consistent electro-thermal calculation with temperature-dependent thermal and electrical resistance required only 0.096 s CPU time. This may suggest that T3D is capable of dealing with complex nets with internal, distributed heat sources.

Figure 7: (a) A two-layer interconnect grid with vias and Joule heat generated on interconnect 3. (b) Implementation in T3D (notice the local maxima on the parabolic temperature trajectories on the extreme segments at each end of interconnect 3).

CONCLUSION

A new method has been introduced to calculate the temperature distribution in non-crimp fibre materials. The net-based approach in Therminator3D can efficiently address the equivalent thermal resistance circuits that incorporate the thermal conductance of each yarn segment. From the test examples conducted, it appears that the speed and accuracy of Therminator3D is very satisfactory, owing to its symbolic solution procedure as well the incorporation of analytical heat solution over each yarn segment. It is also believed that the method can have high potential for solving multi-physics problems of NCFs. A further study is worthwhile to examine the effect of stitching materials in the thermal response of, e.g., glass fibre NCFs. The findings in the studies [1,4] suggest that the stitching threads would have a significant effect on mechanical response of NCFs, partly due to the resulting waviness of the yarns. For effective thermal properties, this effect may or may not be similar. Finally, the incorporation of matrix material into the analysis for prepreg fabrics can be of interest. These and other electro-thermo-mechanical properties can be eventually incorporated in T3D via the netlists.

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